
Research

Enhancing Riverside Park Landscape Design: A County-Level Perspective in China

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Abstract: As China's rapid urbanization intensifies, the nation's focus on green development has become increasingly pressing. Riverside parks, as critical green spaces and landscape nodes, play a vital role in maintaining ecological balance, preserving cultural heritage, and fostering social cohesion in urban areas. However, county-level cities in China often struggle with outdated design concepts and ecological degradation in their riverside parks. This research addresses this knowledge gap by conducting an in-depth examination of the landscape design of riverside parks in county-level areas of China. Through a comprehensive literature review and case studies, this study identifies key challenges and proposes innovative strategies to enhance the landscape design of these parks. The findings of this research provide valuable insights and practical guidance for policymakers, urban planners, and landscape architects seeking to revitalize China's riverside parks and promote sustainable urban development.

Keywords: Riverside Park, Waterfront space, Ecological protection, Cultural expression, Landscaping.

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1. Introduction

China's rapid urbanization has underscored the importance of county-level areas in driving sustainable development. The national policy "Lucid waters and lush mountains are invaluable assets" (also known as "Green water and green mountains are golden mountains and silver mountains") emphasizes the need to prioritize environmental conservation. However, the swift pace of urbanization has taken a toll on the environment [1]. Severe pollution, largely caused by untreated domestic sewage and improper handling of agricultural chemicals, has compromised the health of urban rivers. As the world emerges from the COVID-19 pandemic, people are increasingly seeking solace in nature. The

demand for accessible, well-designed green spaces – particularly riverfront parks – has grown exponentially. Creating such spaces is no longer a luxury, but a necessity for enhancing the quality of life for urban residents.

2. Analysis of Riverfront Park Development in Chinese Counties: Current Situation and Challenges

2.1 Urbanization's Impact on County Riverfront Parks in China

The urbanization process has a multifaceted impact on county-level areas, often accompanied by adjustments and changes in land use structures. As cities expand and populations grow in China, land previously used for agriculture, grasslands, or natural wetlands is repurposed for urban construction or infrastructure development. This transformation significantly alters the land use and scale of county riverfront parks [2]. Urbanization inevitably exerts pressure on the ecological environment, and poor management of county riverside parks can exacerbate these issues, leading to water pollution, ecosystem damage, and biodiversity loss. Furthermore, shifting social needs and lifestyles have increased residents' demands for leisure, entertainment, cultural activities, and natural environments. As a result, riverside parks, as urban green spaces and leisure areas, are affected by these changing demands, influencing their functional positioning and landscape design. The enhancement of modern city images and the importance of urban brand building also impact the development and image of county riverside parks. As vital landscape nodes, these parks must effectively showcase the city's image and characteristics to meet urban development needs. The accelerated pace of urbanization poses challenges to the management and planning of county riverfront parks. As the scale and management needs of these parks increase, more scientific and professional management models and planning methods are required to ensure their sustainable development and effective operation.

2.2 Landscape Design Characteristics of County-Level Riverfront Parks in China

The landscape design of typical riverside parks in Chinese counties often exhibits similarities, with a relatively uniform approach. However, upon closer examination, it becomes apparent that these parks prioritize integrating natural elements and cultural landscapes to showcase local regional characteristics, cultural connotations, and unique landscape charm [3]. To achieve this, designers often preserve the original natural landscape and incorporate local history, tradition, and cultural elements. The proximity of these parks to rivers means that water body guidance and treatment are crucial considerations. Most designs feature well-planned path systems, water corridors, and landscape nodes that enable visitors to engage with the water feature and enjoy various water activities. Facilities such as bridges, trails, and wharves are carefully designed to enhance the overall experience. Given the relatively smaller population of county areas, cost savings are a key consideration. As a result, designers focus on creating a layered spatial sequence through the thoughtful planning and organization of landscape nodes, squares, lawns, leisure facilities, and other features.

This approach provides a wealth of leisure and cultural activity facilities, including children's play areas, fitness facilities, open-air theaters, and cultural squares. By catering to the diverse needs and interests of visitors across different age groups, these parks enrich their functions and activities, ultimately enhancing the overall user experience.

3. Problems and Challenges

Despite the growing sophistication of riverside parks in China's counties, several challenges persist. One key issue stems from the limited land resources available, given that most riverside parks are situated near the central area of the county seat [5]. This scarcity necessitates careful balancing of multiple functions and needs within the confined space. Furthermore, planners and designers must reconcile the dual objectives of riverside protection and development/utilization. Effective ecological environmental protection is also a critical consideration in the landscape design of these parks.

Riverside areas are ecologically sensitive and play a crucial role in maintaining the health of the ecosystem. However, inadequate design measures can have devastating consequences, including the destruction of natural resources such as water bodies, wetlands, vegetation, and wildlife.

Table 1: Summary of Pollutant Inflow into Rivers and Lakes in China

Pollution Source Category	Subcategory	COD (t/a)	NH3-N (t/a)	TN (t/a)	TP (t/a)
Point Source	Industrial Pollution	10,888.97	871.10	0	0
	Urban Life	2,102.06	243.05	338.30	23.65
	Tourism Pollution	55.62	6.43	8.96	0.63
Total (Point Source)	Total	13,046.65	1,120.58	347.26	24.28
Diffuse Source	Rural Domestic Wastewater	3,195.64	779.43	906.51	64.86
	Agricultural Planting	10,766.40	0	3,367.09	308.42
	Scattered Breeding	4,589.11	917.82	1,982.50	624.12
	Aquaculture	19,945.03	0	1,863.86	370.44
Total (Diffuse Source)	Total	38,496.18	1,697.25	8,119.96	1,367.84
Grand Total	Total	51,542.83	2,817.83	8,467.22	1,392.12

This not only harms the ecosystem but also undermines its sustainable development. Another significant challenge is the economic constraint. The financial resources available to county-level areas are limited, which restricts the funding and investment channels for landscape design and construction of riverfront parks. Securing sufficient funds for design, construction, and maintenance is a daunting task, exacerbated by the lack of diversified funding channels and cooperation mechanisms [6]. Effective park construction and management also require the involvement of multiple stakeholders, making social participation and management a critical issue. Ensuring public participation in the decision-making process of landscape design is essential to guarantee that the design plan reflects the needs and opinions of local residents. This, in turn, enhances the park's utilization and user satisfaction, presenting a new challenge that must be addressed.

As integral components of urban development, riverfront parks must be harmoniously integrated with urban planning and development. However, the design of these parks often presents a challenge, as it must balance competing demands: urban functionality, social needs, and environmental protection. Unfortunately, many riverfront parks fall short of their potential, becoming isolated green spaces that fail to seamlessly integrate with surrounding urban areas[7]. This can

result in ineffective design, undermining the park's intended benefits and potential to enhance the overall urban experience.

Table 2: Summary of China's Environmental Governance Economic Investment

4. Current Research Status at Home and Abroad

4.1 China's Approach to Waterfront Development: Evolution and Progress

In recent years, China has undergone significant transformations in its approach to waterfront development. Historically, Confucian ecological thought and "feng shui" theory influenced planning, emphasizing the integration of natural environments and geographical characteristics. However, during the early stages of reform and opening up, economic development pressures led to a decline in ecological protection, resulting in suboptimal waterfront construction [8].

The 1990s saw a global surge in urban waterfront renovation, prompting a renewed focus on domestic waterfront planning. Although China's waterfront development was still in its infancy, it marked the beginning of a new era. By learning from international experience, China has made substantial progress in waterfront planning and development [9]. Notable examples include the Shenyang Coastal Landscape Construction, Dalian Coastal Landscape Construction, and Shanghai Huangpu River Coastal Planning and Design. These projects demonstrate China's growing emphasis on ecological protection and sustainable development principles .

The concept of "landscape city," introduced by renowned scientist Qian Xuesen, has further emphasized the importance of integrating landscape planning into urban construction. This idea has garnered significant attention from experts and scholars, making urban waterfront landscape planning a thriving research field[10].

The Special Plan for Green Landscapes highlights the need for urban waterfront areas to prioritize safe flood discharge, ecological restoration, and ecological economic development. Consequently, the construction of ecological barriers has become a guiding principle for waterfront planning and construction in China.

As urbanization advances in China, researchers are conducting in-depth analyses of urban waterfront development. For instance, studies in Shanghai have investigated landscape characteristics, key control links, and the role of water in urban development. Comparative analyses of domestic and international waterfront planning and construction have also yielded valuable insights, underscoring the importance of water in urban development, leisure, ecological maintenance, and cultural dissemination.

4.2 Urban Waterfront Redevelopment: Global Perspectives and Theoretical Frameworks

The urban waterfront has undergone significant transformations globally. In Europe, the 1980s saw a surge in redevelopment efforts, with notable examples including Liverpool's ship berths and London's Quayside. This trend peaked in subsequent years, garnering widespread attention from experts and scholars. Australia, South Africa, and East Asia have also witnessed exemplary cases of urban waterfront redevelopment, with Japan showcasing unique and innovative approaches in the Asian region.

The Eco-Urbanism Conference, hosted by Harvard, brought the concept of eco-urbanism to the forefront. This platform facilitated the exchange of ideas, promoting in-depth discussions and research on eco-urbanism. The theory's promotion and application have enabled urban landscape design to better integrate with ecosystems, fostering sustainable development and environmental protection [11]. Harvard Design School's advocacy has provided valuable guidance for global city development, driving progress and innovation in urban landscape design.

Western landscape urbanism theoretical research can be broadly categorized into two branches. Moderate landscape urbanism opposes modernist design, emphasizing ecology and the management of urban landscapes and ecological environments. Designers focus on utilizing natural elements, maintaining ecological advantages, and connecting urban elements through landscape design. Successful examples include France's high-speed rail and Barcelona's second ring road, where infrastructure and landscape are seamlessly integrated.

The Chutapi River Park plan exemplifies this approach, incorporating natural elements while preserving the pristine land's natural evolution. This design embodies the concept of respecting the natural environment and promoting sustainable development.

In contrast, radical landscape urbanism focuses on the continuation of a city's social landscape and cultural history. Designers analyze urban landscapes from an architectural perspective, emphasizing the cultural connotations of urban landscape development. Proponents of this approach, including Tschumi, Koolhaas, and Stan Allen, argue that modernism has led to the diversification of cities, causing them to lose their regional and historical context. Radical landscape urbanism seeks to reclaim this context by effectively expressing the cultural significance of urban landscape development. Rem Koolhaas's concept of "landscape" blends traditional urban landscapes with natural landscapes, reflecting the complexities of modern urban environments.

5. Exploration and Improvement

5.1 Integrating Local Culture into Riverfront Park Design in China

In China, the landscape design of riverfront parks at the county level can be enriched by incorporating local culture and integrating historical, cultural, and traditional elements. This can be achieved through the design of architectural styles, landscape elements, sculpture art, and other creative expressions that showcase the unique cultural characteristics of the area, including folk culture and traditional crafts. By doing so, the local charm of the park can be significantly enhanced.

Attention to detail is also crucial in riverside park design. Careful selection and matching of plants, materials, colors, and textures can create a unique landscape atmosphere that reflects local characteristics and styles, making the park truly distinctive. Furthermore, making full use of the natural resources in the riverside area, such as retaining original water features, wetlands, and vegetation, can highlight the uniqueness of the natural landscape. Designing unique ecological landscape elements can also create a natural ecological atmosphere.

Public buildings in the park can be used to showcase local artworks, including sculptures, murals, and installation art, which can reflect the local cultural and artistic characteristics and add a unique artistic atmosphere to the park [12]. This can also indirectly promote local activities, traditional culture exhibitions, folk performances, and local food festivals. By hosting these activities, local characteristics and cultural inheritance can be integrated into the daily operation of the park, enhancing its local charm and uniqueness.

5.2 Catering to Diverse Needs: Multi-Functional Riverfront Parks

Riverfront parks serve diverse user groups, each with unique preferences and needs. While some individuals seek recreational activities, others are interested in sports, fitness, culture, art, or ecological conservation. To address these varied demands, riverfront parks can incorporate multi-functional settings that cater to different interests.

By creating specialized areas for natural ecology, leisure, entertainment, culture, art, water activities, children's play, fitness, and sports, parks can provide a rich and diverse experience. This diversified approach enables parks to attract a broader audience, including tourists and residents, thereby driving the development of surrounding businesses and services.

A well-designed riverfront park can become a vibrant hub of activity, fostering social interaction, promoting physical health, and celebrating local culture. To achieve this, it is essential to adopt a reasonable planning and design approach that integrates various functions into the park's layout. By considering the needs and characteristics of the local population, designers can create a multi-functional and diversified riverfront park that offers a wide range of experiences and services.

5.3 Ecological Environment Protection in County Riverfront Parks

The protection of the ecological environment in county riverfront parks is crucial due to its multiple benefits. The riverside area's ecological environment is a vital natural resource that possesses both protective and utilitarian value. Prioritizing ecological protection effectively safeguards natural resources such as water bodies, wetlands, and vegetation, maintaining ecological balance and ensuring the stability and health of ecosystems.

This approach preserves the natural features and ecological characteristics of the area, enhancing the county's image, attracting tourists and investment, and promoting sustainable local economic development. To achieve this, the design should focus on protecting and restoring the natural ecosystems of the riverfront area.

Key strategies include protecting and increasing vegetation cover, restoring the natural state of wetlands and water bodies, and promoting species diversity[13]. By planning the plant landscape reasonably, selecting local adaptable plant species, and establishing a natural ecological chain, an ecological balance can be created.

Additionally, protecting and improving water quality is essential. This can be achieved by reducing pollutant discharge and input, and enhancing the self-purification capacity of water bodies through ecological wetlands and filtration facilities. Wildlife conservation and habitat creation are also critical aspects of ensuring the park's ecosystem.

Furthermore, sustainable water resources management and utilization are vital. The design should plan water body usage, adopt water-saving measures, and optimize irrigation systems. Promoting water management techniques and awareness can also reduce water consumption.

By protecting and purifying water bodies through ecological means, the quality of water bodies can be improved, and the habitat environment of aquatic organisms can be safeguarded. These measures not only conserve water resources but also provide beautiful water features, increasing the park's landscape appeal.

5.4. Public Participation and Experience in Riverfront Park Design

Public participation and experience are vital to creating an exceptional riverfront park. Enhancing public participation can be achieved by organizing various activities, such as public discussions, symposia, and community events within the park. This encourages residents and visitors to contribute to the park's design decision-making process, sharing their opinions and suggestions.

Utilizing social media platforms can also facilitate public engagement by creating dedicated feedback channels. This enables designers to better understand the public's needs and expectations, ultimately creating a design that aligns with their interests and preferences.

To foster a sense of experience among visitors, the landscape design of the riverfront park should incorporate humanized and diversified concepts. This includes providing a range of facilities and spaces that cater to diverse ages, interests, and needs. Ensuring barrier-free access, convenient amenities, and transportation connections is also essential for facilitating easy entry to the park.

Furthermore, integrating art installations, cultural displays, and activities that reflect local history, culture, and traditions can create an immersive environment with distinct local characteristics. This design approach promotes public recognition, support, and appreciation for the park, ultimately enhancing the image and development of the surrounding county-level area.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the integration of regional characteristics, natural environment, culture, and history is paramount in creating riverfront parks that embody the unique charm and identity of a place. By doing so, we can foster the development of parks with distinct local characteristics, ultimately contributing to the sustainable growth of county-level areas and enhancing the quality of life for residents. However, we must also acknowledge the challenges and limitations faced by riverfront park design in county-level areas, including restricted resources, inadequate funding, and low public participation. To overcome these hurdles, it is essential to explore innovative financing models, cooperative mechanisms, and technological innovations that can augment public engagement and experience. By prioritizing ecological conservation, diversified functional settings, and public participation, we can create vibrant, livable, and sustainable riverfront parks that serve as a model for other regions. As we look to the future, we remain committed to advancing the landscape design of riverfront parks, driven by a shared vision of crafting exceptional, people-centric riverside spaces that enrich the lives of communities.

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